

World Data System – International Technology Office

Describing Catalogues of Services

March 2024

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A REPORT BY THE

World Data System • International Technology Office
Funded under the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (The Alliance)

Cite this report (APA):

Woodford, C.J., Jenkyns, R. (2024). Describing Catalogues of Services. World Data System - International Technology Office.

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vYajtTdoFnEXy86zXykbvn3w7RUGvAvSy0Xi6ohgwdE/e/dit?usp=sharing>

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Executive Summary

This report is intended to outline previous work in describing catalogues of services for research commons, drawing on work by WDS-ITO staff, looking at the landscape of research commons, models of research commons, and recommendations, standards, and conventions from the research infrastructure community. A summary of previous work is followed by a mapping and summary of current descriptions of catalogues of services, current initiatives in the field, and a proposed work plan to collaboratively create concrete deliverables in this area for improved global interoperability of research services. The proposed outputs of the work plan include a semantic object, such as a vocabulary, of agreed-upon terms and descriptions of types of research commons services that may then be used to supplement an existing metadata standard for describing services or seed the creation of a novel metadata standard for services. Ideally, such a standard would then be used by a specific persistent identifier (PID) authority to enable the description and identification of individual services and their use across the research ecosystem.

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Introduction & Background

National, pan national and scientific domain experts around the world are engaged in creating what are referred to as research commons or science commons. At a high level a commons can be defined as a global trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high quality interoperable research outputs and services. The purpose of these commons is to provide digital research resources for the common good.

One of the tasks associated with building a research commons is to create a catalogue of services. These catalogues typically list the data, compute, software resources and ancillary services that are available to researchers to support their investigations.

Part of making science commons interoperable is understanding how different commons administrators are describing their services, with the ultimate goal of ensuring that the service catalogues can communicate and share resources across domain, administrative and geographic boundaries. Catalogues will allow researchers to discover services as well as allow the tracking of service use for citation, evaluation, and assessment purposes. To support that effort, this report combines previous work in identifying types of services to seed the creation of a community-endorsed common vocabulary of types of research commons services. Our goal is that this work will be taken up by an international working group, likely hosted with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and lead to the creation of a service metadata standard and enhanced PID use for services.

WDS-ITO March 2022 report

Previously, WDS-ITO staff conducted a landscape review of current research commons categorization of their services and related initiatives to determine if the global community was converging on descriptions or names for types of services. Their findings were summarized in a report titled “Research Commons Service Catalogues”, completed in March 2022, but was unfortunately not published. They found marked variety in how and if commons described their services, with the most structured example being the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC, 2021). However, there was little consensus at the time between commons on how to describe services. The high level recommended actions from this report are the creation of an international working group to come to community consensus on types and descriptions of services that can then be the basis of an actionable vocabulary.

The current report takes this suggestion further by mapping and combining recent vocabularies describing services for research commons that have been endorsed by the research commons community and proposing specific outputs and a work plan for an international working group.

Research Data Alliance Outputs

The motivation to have a common language to describe not only services but components of a research commons is one of the core goals of the RDA Global Open Research Commons

International Model Working Group (GORC IM WG). This common language takes the form of the GORC International Commons Model (Woodford et al., 2023), which presents a non-prescriptive structured set of considerations for building, developing, expanding, funding, and writing policy for research commons at any scale. The WDS-ITO March 2022 report suggested that the GORC IM WG could focus on catalogs of services as part of the creation of the model, and this was indeed a focused area of work. The model is based on the essential elements of a research commons identified by the GORC Interest Group (IG), which specifically includes “Services & Tools” (Jones et al., 2023). The difference between services and tools with the GORC outputs is that a “service” tends to be enacted on the behalf of the user, whereas a “tool” is used directly by the user. The categorization of services and tools evolved over the course of two significant literature reviews and two separate task groups within the GORC IM WG over the course of nearly 11 months (October 2022 - September 2023). The final organization of service and tool categories was loosely associated with the research lifecycle. A full description of the types of services and tools identified is in the next section, and a list of the resources used to create this list can be found in [Appendix A](#).

Another output of interest from RDA is the [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG](#) currently draft outputs describing the research lifecycle and the services and tools that are used within them. Their first deliverable, an attempt at a universal description of the research lifecycle, was informed by several existing, well known and used models. A full description of the categories of research tools within these research lifecycle stages is in the next section.

Mapping Service Types

The service types identified in the WDS-ITO March 2022 report may be considered captured by those in the GORC model, as many of the research commons considered in the landscape review were also a part of the GORC speaker series or landscape reviews. In particular, the most detailed and clear description of services was provided by EOSC in their V3 profile description (EOSC, 2021). The EOSC V3 and V4 profiles (EOSC, 2022) were both key resources in the development of the GORC model. Therefore, we will consider the mapping needed at this stage to be between the GORC model and the proposed categorization from the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG.

Table 1: GORC model categorization of services and tools for research commons. The labels and descriptions have been altered from the model for clarity and conciseness.

Category	Sub-items
Research Object Repositories	Subcategory
	Research data Repository
	Publication and research documentation Repository
	Research Software Repository
	Semantic Object Repository

Research Object Repositories	Subtype within each subcategory
	API for automated execution of standard Repository tasks and to interoperate with external Services and Tools useful to the stakeholders
	Deposit
	Research Object validation
	Research Object FAIR self-assessment
	Integrity and quality control for Metadata
	Integrity and quality control for Research Objects
	Storage
	Digital badges for Research Objects, with features for online sharing, verification, portability, and trustworthiness with associated Metadata
Discovery Services	Subtypes
	Harvesting, or aggregating, Metadata from external Repositories and commons, including Members and Providers
	Provide a harvestable Metadata Service so that others can harvest Metadata hosted by the commons that describe Research Objects, Services, and Tools.
Services and Tools for direct research tasks	Subcategory
	Data Acquisition
	Analysis, processing, and visualization
	Data collection and Research Object Management
	Subtype within each subcategory
	Consultation services to improve or enable research
	Platform as a Service (PaaS)
Services and Tools that enable workflows and middleware	
Persistent Identifier Services	Subtypes
	Global PID Service that ensures continuous resolvability of PIDs
	Service to discover PIDs from Metadata and vice versa
Vocabulary and Semantic Object Services	

Data management services and tools	
Commons catalogues of all Services and Tools, including those hosting Research Objects	Subcategories
	Registry of Repositories
	Subtypes within each subcategory
	A marketplace or API for external Service Providers to access and add their Services
	Integrity and quality control for Services and Tools
	Registration
Security and Identification Services, Authentication and Authorization (AAI)	Subcategories
	Access protocol translation
	Remote access
	Subtypes within each subcategory
	Cyber security
	User authentication
	Identity access and management
	Authorization
	Assurance
	Group creation and management
Helpdesk	

This reorganization of the “Services & Tools” section of the GORC model does not include all items. Characteristics that cannot be interpreted as subtypes were left out as well as the most granular items. Each item represented here can be paired with its true representation in the model to find examples, consideration levels, and primary sources. Note that services and tools are not mutually exclusive despite being categorized. For example, helpdesk services may assist with repository deposit services. Most service categories are broken down into subcategories and subtypes, where subcategories are more granular services and subtypes are services that are typical within all subcategories of the category, such as storage services for any subcategory of research object repository.

Table 2: A summary of the RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG categories. This was taken from the most recent representation of the [Deliverable 2 in their](#)

[Google Drive workspace](#). Note that this deliverable is not complete or endorsed, and the published version may present a different set of categories when available.

Research Life Cycle Stage	Category
CONCEPTUALISE	Mind mapping, concept mapping and knowledge modelling
	Diagramming and flowchart
	Wireframing and prototyping
FUND	Search
PLAN	Data management planning (DMP)
	Project planning
	Combined DMP/project
COLLECT	Quantitative data
	Qualitative data
	Harvesting
PROCESS	Electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs)
	Scientific computing across all programming languages
	Metadata Tool
ANALYSE	Remediation
	Computational methods
	Computational tools
STORE	Repository
	Archive
	Management
PUBLISH	Discipline-specific data repository
	Generalist data repository
	Metadata repository
PRESERVE	Repository
	Archive
	Transfer
SHARE	Repository

	Electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs)
	Scientific computing across all programming languages
ACCESS	Registry of repositories
	AAI
	Standards
TRANSFORM	Electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs)
	Programming languages
	Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) tools

Although this list is geared towards tools, there are clear overlaps with the GORC model and vice versa as well as between research life cycle stages. A mapping between the two models can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Mapping between GORC International commons model Services & Tools categories (right) and the RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG draft categories of research tools (left).

Notably, most of the service categories identified in the RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG draft deliverable fall under the GORC “Direct Research Tasks” category.

Several are captured by “Repositories” and “Workflows and Middleware”, with multiple GORC categories not being captured in the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG draft. It is clear that the GORC model is more comprehensive, but also that it is intended for a different audience. The GORC model is intended for any and all stakeholders for research commons to interact with, and therefore includes categories of services and tools that are internal to the commons, such as internal data management, which would not belong to any of the research lifecycle stages as it occurs outside the research lifecycle itself and is a sustaining service underlying the ability of a commons to offer other services. Conversely, the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG draft tools categories are intended for researchers only, and so provide a narrower set of possible services but organized in a more intuitive fashion.

It should be said that the purpose of this mapping is not to compare the models in terms of worth. They are intended for different audiences with different purposes, and are only mapped here as they both provide possible categories of services that may be used in a research commons catalog of services. One set of categories is not better than the other in general.

.Figure 2 provides a high level overview of the mapping between the two models. The specific considerations that led to this mapping are:

- Conceptualize → workflows and middleware: The conceptualize stage is focused on tools that enable brainstorming and collaboration, which are specifically listed as examples in this category of the GORC model.
- Plan → direct research tasks, workflows and middleware: The plan stage includes project planning and data management plan (DMP) preparation and creation. The former falls within workflows and middleware, while DMP and RDM services and tools are a subcategory of direct research tasks.
- Fund → workflows and middleware: The fund stage relies on a search tool to find appropriate grants and sustainability opportunities. This would be part of a workflow service if available, but may also be satisfied by discovery services depending on context.
- Collect → direct research tasks: The collect stage is fully captured by the data collection subcategory.
- Process → direct research tasks, workflows and middleware: The process stage specifies access to ICT infrastructure such as computing and the availability of ELNs. These categories are captured by the analysis, processing, and visualization subcategory of direct research tasks. Metadata tools are also a part of the process stage, and are one of specific examples of workflows and middleware services and tools in the GORC model.
- Analyze → direct research tasks: The analyze stage is explicitly part of the analysis, processing, and visualization subcategory.
- Store → repositories, direct research tasks: The store stage includes repositories explicitly as well as archive and management tools. The former two categories are encompassed by the GORC repository category, and management tools are specified as a subcategory in direct research tasks.

- Publish → repositories: While the publish stage could reasonably include the PID category, it is not specified in the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG draft and instead focuses on different types of repositories.
- Preserve → repositories, direct research tasks: The preserve stage could be completely encompassed by the repository category in the GORC model, however transfer services may also be a part of management services within direct research tasks.
- Share → repositories, direct research tasks: Reasonably, the share stage would also include the discovery services GORC model category, however this does not fit with its current categories. As written, the share stage depends on repositories and tools specified within the analysis, processing, and visualization subcategory of direct research tasks.
- Access → Catalogue of services and tools, AAI: The access stage may overlap with the intent of the share stage in the current draft and should be revisited once the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG outputs are finalized. As written, the access stage has clear connection to the AAI category and specifically mentions a registry of repositories, which is a subcategory of the catalogue of services and tools GORC model category.
- Transform → direct research tasks. All of the categories in the transform phase address one or more subcategories of direct research tasks, specifically within data collection and research object management, and analysis, processing and visualization.

Considerations for evolving service types

As highlighted in the WDS-ITO 2022 report, the GORC model, and others referenced here, the typology of services is dynamic and any set of categories will need to be flexible and have a maintenance plan to remain relevant. The mapping above is no different, and any semantic object produced in this area will likewise need to be dynamic and versionable.

Additional considerations beyond sustainability of evolving services types is the distinction between type of service and mode of service. “Type” typically refers to what the service is, whereas “mode” refers to how the service is administered. Both are important considerations for those choosing a service to use in research as well as research commons for describing their services. What we have been focusing on so far in our reports is the type, or categories, of services and not their mode. The service mode should be included in any metadata standard describing services.

Lastly, there is a community movement towards organizing services by stage of the research lifecycle, which does not have a universal definition and is researcher-focused. One potential description and classification of the research lifecycle is [MaLDReTH](#), presented above in Table 2, and the first deliverable of the RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG. MaLDReTH incorporates several high-profile frameworks that describe the research life cycle, and may be used more frequently once finalized and endorsed by RDA. Organizing services by research life cycle may be beneficial for catalogs of services where researchers are the only intended audience, but is limited otherwise. It may be worth considering adding a tag for

research data lifecycle stage on applicable service categories instead of defining the service category by research data lifecycle stage.

Future mappings, scoping reviews, and landscape analysis may consider using the (currently internal) [WDS-ITO curated library of resources](#) as a starting point.

Recommendations

This is an evolving field of work, and no one group or organization can claim to have found the best or most inclusive set of service types to describe catalogs of services for all research commons. Similarly to the work done by the RDA GORC IM WG, community involvement and collaboration increases the likelihood that the outputs will reflect and be used by the stakeholders they describe. We propose to tackle this area of work as an RDA/WDS joint WG.

Commitment from the Alliance and the WDS-ITO should be at least one representative in a co-chair role, and ideally in a lead co-chair role with a research associate committing 0.5 FTE or more to this group. The outputs of this group are highly aligned with the GORC work package, and may be considered a part of this work package.

Outputs & Goals

There are two main deliverables for the proposed WG:

- 1) A semantic object that describes the types of services used in research commons identified from previous work. Ideally this deliverable would be machine-actionable and version controlled, with the possibility of updates and a plan for maintenance.
- 2) A metadata standard for use with a PID for services. This may be a suggested addition of one or more fields for service descriptions in service metadata standards that already exist instead of an entirely new proposed standard.

One possible metadata standard that could adopt the service category descriptions is the Research Services Entity Category (or RS entity) maintained by the Research and Education FEDerations group (REFEDS) (Harris, 2016).

If there was such metadata standard with an associated PID, it would be possible to have federated catalogues of services that target specific communities (e.g. Canada / the Alliance, EOSC, ARDC) and the services within can be compared directly thanks to their shared metadata. This group could also provide mapping from existing systems to the standard as well as mapping between successive versions of the standard so a service only needs to be described once and updated only if the nature of their service changes. A long-term value of these outputs would be the development of a global commons service discovery portal.

Proposed Work Plan

The suggested WDS/RDA WG, if endorsed, can expect to produce deliverables within 18 months. A possible work plan for the WG is:

1. 0-2 months: gather members of main WG, conduct landscape review
 - a. Members of this working group should be drawn from the organizations currently creating Commons, including representatives of the Alliance, the federated identity management (FIM) community, the commercial sector (especially those familiar with the internationally recognized British Information Technology Infrastructure Library (ITIL) and IT service management (ITSM) (ITIL, n.d.) standard), and the VRE/Gateway community. In particular, providers of services in the ecosystem and within WDS membership should be considered, pulling from the GORC IM WG speaker series, members of the RDA. Appropriate discipline and geographic representation for co-chairs and members should be considered.
 - b. A review of the current state of categorization of services, using the WDS-ITO March 2022 report, this mapping in this report, and the internal WDS-ITO library as a starting point to identify rough themes for task groups (TGs)
2. 3-4 months: Landscape review finalized, call for TGs and WG agreement on rough themes
 - a. This likely be a large landscape review due to the field evolving rapidly. It will likely require 3 months of work to adequately capture the field.
 - b. Through discussion, the WG comes to an agreement on the identified themes.
 - c. WG members sign up for one or more TG, which will tackle a theme
3. 4-7 months: each TG refines and confirms their subside of categories
 - a. Within each theme, the TG refines the definition and description of services and identifies categories within the themes. New structures for the ontology may be identified in this phase.
 - b. TGs are encouraged to also consider modes of service delivery for their theme and identified categories.
4. 8-9 months: switch focus of TGs, they review another TGs work (internal peer review)
 - a. In a round-robin fashion, each TG reviews the recommendation of a theme and categories from all other TGs. Recommendations are made, and TGs may meet together to discuss and come to a consensus.
 - b. If possible, host a workshop at an RDA plenary session during this step or the previous step
5. 10th month: full semantic object review by all parties, preparation of communications and final container for first deliverable
 - a. Everyone in the WG reviews the entire suggested semantic object. Ideally, the semantic object will move into a machine-actionable and interactive container that may be showcased to potential adopters.
6. 11-12 months: Identify potential metadata and PID service providers to adopt the service description fields.

- a. This may look like WG discussion meetings, invitation of metadata standard authorities to WG meetings, and TGs testing the viability of either option.
7. 13-14 months: Finalize whether the service descriptions will become part of an existing standard or a modular optional metadata field that can be used in multiple standards.
 - a. If the former, work with the metadata standard authority to incorporate.
8. 15-18 months: finalization of deliverables, communications and adoption coordination

This work plan demonstrates that a common approach to the description and representation for catalogues of services is a feasible exercise to be undertaken by the research data management community. As this report was being completed, the RDA Oracle for Research Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group¹ is finalizing its deliverables with a subset of shared objectives as what is proposed here, with a plenary session scheduled for the RDA P22 in May 2024². A review of their outcomes should be undertaken as part of the conceptualization and landscape review, in order to leverage what they have achieved and avoid duplication of effort.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-ofr-mapping-landscape-digital-research-tools-wg>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/creating-a-categorisation-schema-of-digital-research-tools-mapped-to-the-research-data-lifecycle/>

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